

STAKEHOLDERS

- Figueres city council
- Fisersa
- Agència Catalana de l'Aigua
- Irrigation community of Muga river
- Environmental groups
- Local experts

CHALLENGES

- Droughts management
- Floods prevention
- Water as a natural issue: **water quality and quantity**

AMBITION

- Co-creation of a **global water management plan**, based on a consensus
- Creation of a **new entity** responsible of the **implementation** of the plan
- **Citizen awareness** on water issues
- More **information** provided on water management

INN WATER PARTNERS

A **consortium** gathering 13 organisations (Research and Technology Organisations, SMEs, end users, associations with EU and international coverages).

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INN WATER

Promoting
social innovation
to renew
multi-level and cross-sector
water governance

Pilot Site #3 FIGUERES Spain

Led by

Ajuntament de Figueres
www.visitfigueres.cat

FIGUERES

The Muga watershed is bordered to the East by the Mediterranean Sea, to the north by the limits of France and the mountains of the Serra de l'Albera and Serra de les Salines and to the West and South by other river basins.

METHOD

1. Set the composition of pilot site community
2. Assess the current water governance situation
3. Set objectives and planning
4. Test and implement schemes and tools
5. Feedback and assessment

5 PILOT SITES

Implementing different types of governance mechanisms and covering different **water challenges**, test and co-develop the tools and methods.

INN WATER
Pilot Site Community

France, Réunion Island - **Economic focus**

Italy, Middle Brenta Basin - **Ecosystem services & Drinking water sector**

Spain, Figueres - **Water scarcity**

United Kingdom, West Country - **Water quality**

Hungary, Middle Tisza - **Water allocation**

